

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B421
 Date: 17 Dec 2008
 Take Off: 14:00:26
 Landing: 17:56:50
 Flight Time: 3h 56m 24s

Campaign: APPRAISE instrument test

Operating Area: SW approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
6	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
7	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
8	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	
9	CVI / FWVS	Paul Barrett	Met Office	
10	AMS	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
11	Manc Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester University	
12	Manc Cloud Training	Chris Dearden	Manchester University	
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

The following log sheets are not available for this flight :

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump / filter info included on Flight Summary page
CVI / FWVS	No CVI log available / no FWVS log is taken
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	29 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_102145_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_112145_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_122145_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_132145_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_132145_1hz.avi
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 faam-video-ffc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_122132_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_132132_1hz.avi
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faam-video-rfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_102136_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_112136_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_122136_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_132136_1hz.avi
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faam-video-ufc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_102141_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_112141_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_122141_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_132141_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20080416_r0_b357_142141_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B421
 Date: 17 December 2008
 Project: APPRAISE test flight
 Location: SW approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
134348		Video	0.28 kft	135	recording
134406		shutters	0.28 kft	135	closed
134737		Start-Up	0.28 kft	135	
135325		ASP	0.28 kft	073	open
140026		T/O	0.28 kft	212	Cranfield
140026	140730	Profile 1	1.4 - 10.0 kft	317	from surface to fl100
140547		nev	8.2 kft	352	zero
140626		JW	9.2 kft	339	zero
140819	141540	Run 1	10.0 kft	242	
141540	142317	Profile 2	10.1 - 18.0 kft	250	
142317	143320	Run 2	18.0 kft	266	
142339		!	18.0 kft	266	r2 fl180
142359		!	18.0 kft	266	psap flow off (cloud)
142421		BBR	18.0 kft	266	retract
143320	143751	Profile 3	18.0 - 22.0 kft	246	
143346		BBR	18.3 kft	245	extend
143752	145612	Run 3	22.0 kft	261	
143947		BBR	22.0 kft	269	retract
144015		nev	22.0 kft	267	zero
144057		JW	22.0 kft	266	zero
145612	151849	Profile 4	22.0 - 1.0 kft	023	
151043		p4	6.8 kft	358	interrupt
151233		p4	6.8 kft	018	resumed
151859		!	1.00 kft	011	manouvre
151943	152944	Run 4	1.0 kft	273	1000ft
152159		JW	1.0 kft	266	zero
153041	153251	Profile 5	1.1 - 0.06 kft	179	
153251	153759	Run 5	0.06 - 0.04 kft	175	
153311		r5	0.05 kft	175	100ft
153810		!	0.16 kft	173	manouvre
153951	155735	Profile 6	0.67 - 22.0 kft	035	
154041		heimann	1.4 kft	046	cal07
154128		heimann	2.4 kft	049	cal command ignored
154402		heimann	5.4 kft	000	cal 08 ok
155306		cloud top	16.8 kft	181	
155806		!	22.0 kft	269	manouvre
160007	161009	Run 6	19.5 kft	314	
160018		!	19.5 kft	315	fl195
161117		!	19.5 kft	109	manouvre
161135	161510	Profile 7	19.5 - 15.5 kft	128	
161510	162519	Run 7	15.5 kft	192	
162520	162658	Profile 8	15.5 - 13.5 kft	347	
162709		!	13.5 kft	359	manouvre
162854	163926	Run 8	13.5 kft	167	
163648		BBR	13.5 kft	227	signal check ok
163926	164202	Profile 9	13.5 - 11.5 kft	334	
164202	165202	Run 9	11.5 kft	347	
165202	165410	Profile 10	11.5 - 10.0 kft	348	
165411	170411	Run 10	10.0 kft	133	
170412	170527	Profile 11	10.0 - 9.0 kft	115	
170527	171751	Run 11	9.0 kft	115	
171828		!	9.3 kft	113	pop up to fl100
171924	172632	Run 12	10.0 kft	114	fl100
172315		heimann	10.0 kft	077	cal05
172632	173314	Profile 12	10.0 - 3.6 kft	070	
173345	174348	1st procedure	3.5 - 0.31 kft	083	
174348	174414	go around	0.31 - 0.85 kft	213	
174414		2nd procedure	0.85 kft	218	
175650		Land	0.27 kft	210	

B421 11:44:10-18:03:43

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

Sortie Brief: APPRAISE-Clouds – Test Flight

Date: 17 Dec 2008. Flight Number: B421

T/O time: 14.00z (3 hour flight)

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To flight test a large fraction of the instrumentation fit that will be used in future APPRAISE-Clouds science flights. This will include examination of the performance of the wing mounted cloud microphysics probes, and a comparison of the output from the recently rejuvenated wing mounted PCASP with the internally mounted instrument on the CVI inlet when the latter is operating in aerosol mode.

Sortie Location: Area Alpha to the West of SW England/Wales and S of Ireland in cloud associated with an approaching warm front which is forecasted to be along the east coast of Ireland at around 2-3pm.

Sortie Summary: A number of straight and level runs will be carried out at a series of altitudes (and hence temperature levels) in cloud associated with the warm front at mid and higher levels, to test the operation of the cloud microphysics instrumentation. In addition, runs below cloud will undertaken to test aerosol instrumentation both external and internal to the aircraft. It is preferential that some of these out of cloud measurements should be undertaken within the boundary layer so as to compare probes at higher aerosol concentrations, as well as the lower concentrations that will be seen at higher levels. It is unlikely that there will be any cloud over the Chilbolton Radar facility at the time of the flight, but a courtesy communication with the facility by VHF radio should be established to advise the facility of our objectives for the remainder of the flight.

Sortie Detail:

- a) T+0 Take off & climb to FL100 (or another appropriate flight level) to transit to operating area to west of SW England/Wales.
- b) When in a suitable location descend from transit altitude to 1000ft agl, or to lowest altitude allowed by operating restrictions. Fly a leg in **clear air** for at least 15 mins in the boundary layer. AMS/SMPS to operate of Rosemount inlet.
- c) Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min along the azimuth and through the cloud system up to FL330 or to above mid level cloud top, whichever is lower
- d) Fly a series of SLRs at a number of different altitudes in cloud as determined by the mission scientist from observations during previous profile ascent. During incloud legs the Mission Scientist will request AMS and SMPS to switch to sample off the CVI inlet. The CVI operator may request runs to be undertaken near to cloud levels but out of cloud in order to adjust inlet flows. In this case the pattern of SLRs will be adjusted accordingly. Item c) may also be interrupted below cloud base for this calibration. Out of cloud AMS/SMPS will operate off the Rosemount inlet – except in the case of CVI flow calibration.
- e) Where a feature of interest is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, or a layer of interested is identified, the feature/layer may be investigated further by carrying out additional legs at that level and/or may include other flight patterns such as a butterfly pattern through the feature*.
- f) Repeat items d) to e) as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit or until mission objectives are achieved.
- g) End mission with another below-cloud clear air aerosol leg (at least 10 min) before climbing to transit level for recovery to Cranfield.

* A butterfly pattern consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern.

PROJECT BRIEF: APPRAISE-Ice – mixed-phase cloud studies

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems, altocumulus clouds, wave clouds and cumulus clouds within the temperature regime in which ice particles will likely co-exist with liquid (typically 0 to -30C).

The flight plans are designed to characterise the aerosol above and below the cloud and infer aerosol fluxes into the cloud layer by combination with the vertical wind measurements and the microphysical characteristics within the cloud layer.

Constant altitude flight legs of approximately 50 km (10 minutes flying) will be made:

- In the boundary layer to measure the aerosol size distributions (from 10 nm to 100 um), CCN, aerosol composition from 30 nm to 1 um using the ToF AMS; larger particles and non-volatile material such as refractory material will be measured using EDAX analysis of filter samples.
- Near cloud base within cloud to measure the cloud droplets that have been activated from CCN, interstitial particles and larger particles that have fallen from cloud top. In addition the onset of ice will be observed using the CPI, SID-2 and 2-D probes in cloud.
- Middle of the cloud passes will be made at temperatures where key processes will be expected to be initiated (-6C to -9C) for the Hallett-Mossop process or around -15C where fragmentation of dendritic crystals may be important.
- Near cloud top and within the cloud to measure entrainment and aerosols within entrained eddies and ice particles within the cloud; in colder clouds ice initiation will occur in this region.
- Above the cloud to measure the properties of aerosol particles that can potentially be entrained into the clouds.

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the CAMRa radar and lidar facilities at Chilbolton, Hants.

Weather conditions: Stratiform, or altocumulus clouds lying over or to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- CPI and 2DS, CAPS and FSSP – as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.
- AMS, SMPDS/WCPC (- ability to sample off both Rosemount and CVI inlets)

Inlets: CVI inlet will be required for sampling of incloud residuals by AMS & SMPS

Mission Scientist Debrief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies: Test Flight 1

Flight Number: B421, 17 Dec 2008 (Take-off 14:00 Landing 17:57)

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To flight test a large fraction of the instrumentation to be used in APPRAISE-Clouds science flights in Jan-March 2009. This was to include an examination of the performance of the wing mounted cloud microphysics probes, and a comparison of the output from the recently rejuvenated wing mounted PCASP with the internally mounted instrument on the CVI inlet with the latter operating in aerosol mode.

Weather conditions & operating area: A frontal system was approaching the British Isles from the west. The associated warm front was forecasted (00Z model run) to lie over the west coast of Wales in a NE-SW orientation by around 15:00GMT, trailing off to the SW (W of Bristol Channel and Cornwall). The aim was to fly in the cloud associated with this front to west of SW UK as it approached from the W with a 14:00 takeoff time. Once airborne it was clear there was little cloud in the region SW of Pembrokeshire, the front being somewhat weaker in this region and with the majority of cloud appearing further to the N over Cardigan Bay and the Irish Sea. Although normally a restricted military area permission was granted for us to operate in this Cardigan Bay area to flight test the instrumentation in cloud.

Summary of the flight: After take-off and climbing out from Cranfield (P1) the initial transit (R1) was at FL100 in clear air heading for the airline over the Brecon area. After a climb (P2) to FL180 cloud was encountered over the borders of Wales. The cloud was mixed phase (at -20degC) and consisted small drops and aggregates. AMS was set to sample residuals from the CVI (and did not see the high organic loading observed when sampling from CVI in wet clouds in VOCALS). Manchester cloud instruments were reported as working fine as was 2DC. 2DP was reported as being noisy following the profile ascent and large T change. On the ascent and clear air legs PCASP reported low concentrations (hence leaks seemingly cured). CO was not being logged to Horace. The reason for this was not clear. After 5 minutes in fairly thick cloud the cloud thinned, the sun's disc could be seen to the SW, and then the aircraft entered clear air over S Wales. The AMS remained on CVI for flow checks.

Following a profile climb to FL220 (P3) it was clear there was little cloud in the planned operating area to the SW, while in the distance to the NW fairly extensive cloud was visible. At this transit level (R3) PCASP measured zero counts and CAS reported little or nothing too. The PCASP off the CVI in aerosol mode reported the same zero. AMS and SMPS also saw nothing. 2DP was again very noisy reporting large numbers. This noise reduced in time (to as low as 10-20 counts/m³) – presumably as the different elements of the probe approached the same temperature.

At the end of R3, the aircraft turned to begin profile descent P4 to 1000ft, initially heading NE towards and over Pembrokeshire. CVI reported the water CPC (CCN or AMS?) was reading 400 cm⁻³, while the 3010 on the CVI inlet saw 140 cm⁻³ and PCASP saw 10 cm⁻³. Externally the PCASP was reporting 0-5 cm⁻³. At 15000ft a thin cloud layer was seen ahead and the PCASP report 20 cm⁻³ (its highest reading for a while!), 2DP was reported to have settled down just before the start of P4 but it was now noisy again, 2DC was seeing “stuff” falling from above. During an interrupt to P4 at 6.7kft (to reset WCPC on AMS rack) the 2DP noise decreased a lot. P4 resumed and the aircraft headed out over Cardigan Bay to continue the descent to 1000ft. R4 at 1000ft above the sea was carried out west of Barmouth heading west. PCASP recorded 20 cm⁻³ while CAS was seeing around 2 cm⁻³. CVI reported that the WCPC was seeing 700 cm⁻³ while the CVI 3010 was seeing 400 cm⁻³. The CVI PCASP was 35 cm⁻³ and falling. The AMS was seeing very low loadings, the SMPS numbers were low and noisy but appeared to be bimodal with a sub 100nm mode and another around 200nm. Halfway through the run core cloud (2DC?) was not seeing precipitation particles although CVI was seeing larger particles. CPI reported seeing such particles. Shortly after precipitation could be seen on the windscreen, appearing as small streaky drizzle drops. R4 was clearly pretty clean so it was decided to profile down to 100ft (P5) and carry out a low level run above the sea surface at 100ft (R5) both heading south. Unfortunately aerosol loadings remained low so a plan was hatched to do a missed approach to Cranfield before landing to get some aerosol measurements in a higher concentration environment.

A profile ascent (P6) was started from 0.6kft up FL220 in the area of northern Cardigan bay and to the west of the Llyn peninsula. At 7.8kft CPI reported seeing some ice. CPI, 2DS and CPI reported crystals as large as 100µm. 2DC also reported ice. Above 11.5kft it saw concentrations of 10-20 per litre and this agreed with CPI/2DS. At 14.2 kft CPI

reported it was gently snowing, and as it was Christmas mince pies were served shortly after! Cloud top was seen at around 16.8kft but another cloud layer could be seen above so it was decided to continue the ascent up to that level. 2DP was still behaving well. CPI reported crystals of between 10 and 600 μ m. 2DC was seeing concentrations of about 1 litre-1. At the end of P6 (FL220) the aircraft was just through CT so it was decided to drop back into the upper level cloud to carry out SLR R6 at FL195. At -23degC the 2DP was once again very noisy. 2DC was seeing 200 μ m crystals, while 2DS saw an increase to 500 μ m crystals which 2DC then agreed with. At the end of the R6 ice was reported on the airframe, and then CPI reported seeing a lot of small drops. It was decided to profile down (P7) to the main cloud layer below. Although the forward facing camera had iced up the turbulence probe remained clear of ice. Wing canisters were clear too, but the CVI tip (supposedly at -46degC) was iced up.

At FL155, R7 (at -14.3degC) started initially in a cloud free gap but then went into cloud. 2DP was still reporting negative concentrations but 2DC was fine and seeing 20-50 cm-3. PCASP was seeing 10 litre-1 at the start, and FFSSP and FSSP were reported as OK. Later 2DS and CPI saw dendrites, CAS saw a mode at 2-5 μ m, CIP an amorphous blob, while CVI was reported as working well and seeing similar features to the cloud probes. The water CPC was however seeing 17000 particle /cm3 – clearly incorrect. FSSP concentration generally agreed with CAS.

A profile descent (P8) to FL135 (at -11.1degC) was undertaken and SLR R8 started initially out of cloud. Multiple cloud layers could be seen, and soon cloud was sampled. Again large dendrites were observed by 2DS and CPI. 2DC saw a concentration of 10 litre-1 and during the profile (P9) down to FL115 saw either really small particulate (<100 μ m) or particles larger than the field of view (800 μ m). 2DP concentrations were now positive but still unreliable. During R9 at FL115 (at -6.8degC) CPI reported entering thick water cloud, with some ice in it. The CVI tip became solidly iced up with no flow through it. Occasional out of cloud segments were sampled and at other times cloud drops with larger precipitation sized particles were observed (CPI). 2DP had much reduced noise by the end of R9.

A profile (P10) down to FL100 (at -3.7degC) was undertaken. During R10 (heading back towards land over Wales) rain was seen and aircraft anti-ice was activated. CPI saw large crystals up to 1000 μ m in size which were pristine columns as well as drops and irregulars. The CVI was now deiced and so AMS was switched to that inlet. 2DP was also now getting “good” data along with 2DC, PCASP and FFSSP. The latter agreed with FSSP which saw a concentration of 50 cm-3 with a peak around 16-17 μ m. CDP saw the same concentration and the spectra were also similar. CAS saw around 125 cm-3 with a peak around 2.5-3 μ m. Over the coast, a profile descent (P11) to the requested level of FL90 transiting back across Wales was undertaken and R11 (FL90, -1.6degC) was carried out in clear air. Over the midlands, an ascent to FL100 was carried out to transit back to Cranfield in an airplane (R12, -3.15degC). PCASP concentrations were reported to be around 10 cm-3 but CAS was seeing zero counts. The aircraft carried out a missed approach to Cranfield airport getting down to a minimum altitude of 50ft agl before landing (17:56:50), hopefully providing some high concentration aerosol data.

Notes on instrumentation:

CO - was running OK but was not logged to the system. The reason for this has not yet been identified

WCPC – PC not networked so could not see in flight

2DP – upset by changes in temperature leading to excessive noise – settled down if T was relatively constant in flight. Need to determine if this makes instrument viable for

APPRAISE

CVI – tip froze up leading to zero sample flow. In any case question mark against sampling philosophy if any ice is on tip. 1) It was agreed running SP2 pump in flight (in absence of SP2) helps. 2) need to look at bypass plumbing option.

FFSSP – phantom distribution appeared on second CDAS system

General observations from flight:

A mobile phone was left on during flight. It is possible for this to interfere with the auto pilot so extra care must be taken to ensure phones are turned off when told to do so

Mission Scientist's Log

(APPRAISE - Test 1)

Flight No B.421... Date 17/12/08... Name K.N. BOWER... Page 1 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
13:52.49	(KNB time)				Taxi (1014, 300ft)
13:56.18 - 13:57.29					Holding on RW 18
14.00:25	(KNB H)				Rolling
14.00.54	(KNB H)				T/O Bright-sunny - low level clouds
14.05.50	Climb S.	7000ft			Climbing to FL100
14.07:14	Climb/End/R1s	FL100	256°	52°18'/0°30'	-3.62°/-11.45°C 696mb 20ms/307' Clear Air.
14.15.39	R1E/P2S	FL100			Climbing to FL180 - cloud ahead
14 21.30	(14 21.30 = 14 22.00 KNB)				(@ not logging (OK on mask) - not on display) (TIME CHECK) for earlier times 300-500 on WPCP. (maybe over in mode) ^{SMS}
14.23.15	P2E/P2S	FL180	266°	51°48'/2°12'	505mb -19.99/-20.08°C 27ms/326° [Over Gloucester]
					Ahead to enter cloud - CVI → Cloud
					mixed phase - small drops + aggregates.
					2DC - fine
					2DP - noise (not OK)
					PCASP - low levels conc on way up
14.26.30	R2	FL180			AMS OK - near on CVI - not seeing head of Obj - from CVI
					Still mixed phase - ice now dom - plebs at -19°C
14.29.50	R2	FL180			We were in thick cloud - near into a hole - could see sun's disk before Photo in hole.
					2DC - 13/litre
					PCASP - 10/cos³
14.32:10	R2	FL180			2DP - poss seeing 7000/m³ - noisy

Mission Scientist's Log

(APPRAISE - Test 1)

Flight No B...⁴²¹..... Date 17/12/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 2 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					5/cm ³ small drops
					0.2/cm ³ ice
14.33.16	P2E/P3S	FL180	246°	51°36'/3°18'	-20.8/-16.59°C 25m/s/317° S05mb (Over MetNet)
					into clear air again...
					AMS on CVI - flow checks
14.35.30	P3	19600ft			-Bright Sunline - thin cloud layers around - not that much above h ₀ - will stop P3
14.37.49	P3E/R3	FL220	260°	51°30'/3°48'	- Clear air - CVI → aerosol - at PCASOS
				[crossed out Part Talbot]	PCASO - nothing -28.97/-30.96
					CAS - little or nothing 427mb 26m/s/320°
					CVI - aerosol mode - PCASO is nothing
					ZDP - very noisy - sees particles when there
					ZDP - "fake one" - decreasing - maybe equilibration
					- give it 5 more minutes to see if it settles.
					- ZDP - bottom - 10-20 cnt/h ³
					- AMS seen nothing - SMPS too
					- CO mt coming up on Horner.
14.52.28	R3	FL220	277°	51°18'/5°30'	- modest seeing ice falling -29.22/-29.44°
14.55.10	R3 turn	FL220	295°	1/5°48' (NB:	N ₂ SO ₂ on trucking) 428mb 25m/s/300°
14.56.09	R3 end/P4	FL220	22°	51°24'/5°48'	Descent now -29.19°C/-30.09° 427mb 25/303°
					CVI report: WCPC → ~ 400
					EVI (CPC ~ 140, PCASO ~ 10)
					PCASO - 0-5 cm ⁻³ - smallest ions
		15000			Cloud layer thin - clear
					PCASO - 20 to highest!

Mission Scientist's Log

(APRIMSE - Test)

Flight No B.....421

Date17/12/08

NameK.N. BOWER

Page 3 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Core Cloud ZDP - had settled down before P4
					- now noisy - ZDP seeing some stuff
					Falling out from above - ZDS/CPL too
	P4 int			52°0/4°42'	AMS - needed to rearm CPC (-1.36/2.49°C) (18ms/300')
					ZDP noise decreasing as we were level
15.12.29	P4 resume	6.7kft	15°	52°12'/4°42'	Resuming descent -1.04/-2.7°C 788mb 18/295°
15.15.47	P4 end	1.0kft	17°	52°30'/4°24'	975mb 6.26/3.52° 14ms/255° (West of Barmouth)
15.15.59	Manuvers	1000			PCASP ~ 20cm² CAS ~ 2cm²
15.19.40	R4 st	1000	275°	52°36'/4°24'	CVI WPC - 700 976mb 6.41/4.49°C
					↓3010: CPC - 400 14ms/233°
					CVI PCASP - ~ 35 and drench
					AMS - low readings
					SNPS - low No's - noisy - in a modal
					modus: sub 100 + 200ms
					Core PLASP
					CAS Run 0.6 - rather > 5µm
					- Core Cloud - no ppt
					CVI - spray or ppt? CPI yes
15.25.01	R4				ppt: on windscreen - streaky - small drops
15.26.10	R4				ZDP - 20/m³ - CLEAN so will
					ZDS - ? Do 100ft Run...
					CIP ~ up to 100/µhr
15.29.42	P4 E	1000	265°	52°36'/5°15'	976mb - Very Clean 6.71/3.84° 14ms/238°
15.30.38	P5 S	1000	180°	52°30'/5°15'	↓ 100ft 6.97/1.48° 976mb, 14ms/239°
15.32.48	P5E/RS	100ft	174°	52°24'/5°15'	1012mb OKH 9.36/5.15° 12ms/235°

(Conductivity Bias W Abrasion)

2 hrs in area.

Mission Scientist's Log

(ARRANSIE - Trd)

Flight No B...421 Date 17/12/08 Name K.W. BOWEN Page 4 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
15.37.55	R5E	100ft (OAT)	174°	52°12'/5°12'	1011mb 9.67°/5.48° 11m/s/240° Not much clouds
15.39.48	P6	0.6kft	35°	52°6'/5°6'	(1014) 958mb 7.75°/4.49° 13m/s/252°
15.45 ish					CPI - seeing some ice
15.46.48	P6	7.8kft	359°	52°30'/4°48'	CIP } 758mb 0.51°/-1.45° 21m/s/300° CPO } CPI } ice up to 100µm
					2DC
					2DC - seeing stuff in to....
		11.5kft			Cinc - low
					2DC - 10-20 µm lit CIP/2DS agree
15.51.06	P6	14.2kft	106	52°42'/4°30'	-CPI - gully sunny - Christmas (-10.9°/-14.5°C) 25m/s/295°
15.53.11	P6	16.8kft	183	52°36'/4°24'	just out of CT, (529mb, -16.97°/-18.94°C) 22m/s/293°
					10µm - 600µm - ⇒ dead above - yes
					2DC: 1/µm lit 2DP - ∅
					3DP - still OK at moment
15.57.32	P6E	PL220	216	52°12'/4°18'	- Above/out of dead - diving down into the dead 425mb, -28.35°/-34.06° 22m/s/295°
					2DP - get rising again!
16.00.09	P6 S	PL195	314	52°15'/4°36'	-23.1°C / -24.77°C, 474mb, 28m/s/297°
					2DC seeing peaks - 200µm
					2DS - seen stuff at 500 - 2DC agrees - ↑ size
16.08.12					2DC - 5-10 µm
16.10.05	P6 E	PL 195	352	52°42'/5°12'	Drop down to 150 (detects ice - air frame)
					2DC - dropped out again 474mb -23.79°/22.31°C
					29m/s/289°

CPI - lit small drops not big fresh probs other probes - ...

Mission Scientist's Log

(APPRAISE - tent)

Flight No B.....421 Date17/12/08 NameKN BOWEN Page 5 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
16:11:33	R7 ST	FL195	128°	52°42' / 5° 6'	474mb -23.59/-22.07°C 26m/s/292° Find focus camera - veed up (Flight Man) Turbo probe clear - comms clear - clear too CWI tip veed up (out (40°C) too)
16:15:07	R7E/ R7S	FL158	191	52°30' / 5° 4'	-14.2°C / -14.9°C 556mb 23m/s/255°
16:16:44	R7	FL155			gap → then into dead 2DP - weird things - ve comms ?? 2DC - fine - 20-50 cm? PCASP ~ 10/mbar FSSP / PFSSP OK. CPI - CAS -2-5/cm ³ made 2.5mm CIP large amorphous lsh 2DS } dendrites CPI } CWI - gain well - similar to dead probe PCASP - CWI - not seeing a lot now. but - WPC - 17000 !!! FSSP only ~ 1cm → (agrees with CAS → CWI CAS 1-160 cm ³
16:25:09	R7E/ R7S	FL158	346°	52°42' / 5° 12'	559mb -15.18/-12.54°C 26m/s/29° V probe -15 high clear Wb.
16:25:50	R7E	FL135	348	52°48' / 5° 12'	605mb -11.17/-10.32°C 28m/s/307°
16:28:54	R7S	FL135	167	52°48' / 5° 0'	Initially out of dead - may head into dead - multi layers of dead here. -11.1/-9.99°C 606mb 23m/s/302°

Mission Scientist's Log

(APPROXISE - F.d)

Flight No B.....⁴²¹ Date^{17/12/08} Name^{K.N Bowen} Page⁶ of⁷

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					ZDC - 10/Litre
					ZDC/CR large dendrite - ppt
					ZDP +ve No snow!
16.39.23	R9/RA	FL135	332°	52°12'/5°0'	606mb -10.24°/-10.07° 26 m/s/292°
					ZDC - really small at 100µm or larger than field of view
16.41.58	R9/RA	FL115	348°	52°16'/5°0'	-6.72°C / -5.68°C 655mb 29m/s/302°
	R9.	FL115			CP1 - just entered thick water cloud. - with some ice in it!
					CVI tip completely iced up - ice
					- Out of cloud - back in eye
					White caps on diamond lakes
16.44	R9	FL115			- CP1: few dust drops Some larger ppt too
16.50					ZDP - noise - reduced snow
16.51.56	RAE/PI0	FL115	348°	52°54'/5°6'	-6.87° / -5.08°C, 24 m/s/295, 656mb
16.54.05	PI0E/PI0S	FL100	141	52°54'/5°6'	-3.74° / -3.81°C 16 m/s/4°, 696mb.
					cloud layer rain - ppt
					anti ice on too on a/c
					CP1 - larger up to 100µm pristine column 2 drops + irregular
					CVI - decal so AMS → CVI now
					CP1 - ZDP - again some good del.
					ZDC

CPD } sample spectra - under resolution
 F550 }
 F2 F550 - line 3 - core Max 50/om²
 CPD - 50 om² mid 60-70µm 16-17
 1000. ca. 10.1 km - max!

Mission Scientist's Log

(APPROXISE - TST)

Flight No B.....421 Date 17/12/08 Name K. N BOWEN Page 7 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
17.04.04	R10E/R11S	FL100	115	52°36'/4°0'	696mb -3.89°C/-3.85° 25m/s/310°
17.05.26	R11E/R11	FL90	115	52°30'/3°48'	Clear of cloud here - none above as we go East. over Wales. -1.61°/2.45° 723mb 36/351°
17.18.01	R11E	FL90	114	52°6'/2°15'	just after end R11 -2.28°/-2.87° 17m/s/325° 722mb -2.28°/-2.87°C 722mb
19.19.22	R2S	FL100	114	52.6°/2°12'	-3.73°/-3.97°C 697mb 21m/s/315°
17.26.22	R12E/R12	FL100	66		-3.15°/-4.45°C 696mb 25m/s/318° PCASO - 10/cm ³ CR1 where are these - cloud in ch1 and ch2 CR3 - zero.
17.57.20					Landed <u>NB</u> Approach Cranfield from W, then head NE and then N to do R11 turn for missed approach down to SDF. along R/W alignment NE → SW - Aerod tests
Debrief - Instruments:-					
CO - running OK - not logged at all on Moacc.					
WCPC - PC not returned - couldn't see in High					
ZDP - upset by changes in Temp → excessive noise - settle down if T constant.					
CWI bus huge up → zero flow - run SP2 mid flight - helps - need to look at bypass option					
phantom F95P dust on CDAS-2 systems !!					
TW good					
Mobile Phone left on - could interfere with Avio pilot					

NB Pilots in simulator on Jan 5th - Flight on 6th would be high
Teleconference 9.30 Jan 5th.

2019 12/10/2019

CO

W CPC ← no return

2DP

CVI tip hys up - run SP2 pump.

- web site bypass option

Support FSSP data appearing in CDAS
door bill et console.

TW data good.

Mobile Phones.

Pilots in simulator on Monday 5th

End of climb to FL100

Flight B421 14:11:56
Heading 251 deg Speed 262 knots Height 10.0kft Press 696mb
Lat 52°12.0'N Long 1°0.0'W Wind 20 ms-1/ 309 deg
Temp -3.97C Dewpoint -7.32C
From 14:00:00 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -1.05 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
GIN LATITUDE 52.2 deg (+ve N)

End Transit R1 , start P2

End P2 start R2 at FL180

Flight B421 14:29:11
Heading 265 deg Speed 275 knots Height 18.0kft Press 505mb
Lat 51°42.0'N Long 2°48.0'W Wind 27 ms-1/317 deg
Temp -20.06C Dewpoint -19.55C
From 14:00:00 to now

Current values			
++++	PRESSURE HEIGHT	18.02	Kft
++++	NEPH BLUE SP	5.06	m-1
++++	NEPH GREEN SP	4.68	m-1
++++	NEPH RED SP	3.89	m-1

Flight B421 14:31:17
Heading 265 deg Speed 276 knots Height 18.0kft Press 505mb
Lat 51°42.0'N Long 3°6.0'W Wind 25 ms-1/319 deg
Temp -20.02C Dewpoint -19.77C
From 14:00:00 to now

Current values			
++++	PRESSURE HEIGHT	18.02	Kft
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-20.02	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-19.77	deg C

End R2 start P3

End P3 start R3 at FL220 out of cloud

CPI seeing ice falling from above - 2DC too

Turning at FL220

End R3 start P4 from FL220 to 2000ft

Flight B421 15:05:09
Heading 22 deg Speed 246 knots Height 12.0kft Press 643mb
Lat 51°48.0'N Long 4°48.0'W Wind 26 ms-1/306 deg
Temp -6.82C Dewpoint -9.07C
From 14:00:00 to now

Current values
++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT 12.05 Kft All
++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP -6.83 deg C
++++ DEW POINT -9.07 deg C

Plot - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Lat 52°0.0'N Long 4°42.0'W Wind 18 ms-1/ 300 deg
Temp -1.36C Dewpoint -2.47C

neph alt Plot From: 14:00:00 To: now -

Save plot parameters as neph alt

Y 579.PRESSURE HEIGHT (Kft)

- 614.ORGANIC H2O2 MR (ppb)
- 619.CABIN PRESSURE (mb)
- 620.NEPH PRESSURE (mb)
- 621.NEPH TEMPERATURE (K)
- 622.NEPH BLUE SP (m-1)
- 623.NEPH GREEN SP (m-1)
- 624.NEPH RED SP (m-1)

X1 622.NEPH BLUE SP (m-1)	Blue	Cross	Del
X2 623.NEPH GREEN SP (m-1)	Green	Cross	Del
X3 624.NEPH RED SP (m-1)	Red	Cross	Del
X4			
X5			

P interrupt - AMS CPC correction

P4 resume

Flight B421 15:17:18
 Heading 17 deg Speed 212 knots Height 2.4kft Press 925mb
 Lat 52°30.0'N Long 4°30.0'W Wind 15 ms-1/ 269 deg
 Temp 3.02C Dewpoint -0.27C
 From 14:00:00 to 14:56:00

Current values
 ++++ STATIC PRESSURE 925.85 mb
 ++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP 3.02 deg C
 ++++ DEW POINT -0.27 deg C

Flight B421 15:16:43
 Heading 18 deg Speed 211 knots Height 3.0kft Press 905mb
 Lat 52°24.0'N Long 4°30.0'W Wind 13 ms-1/ 271 deg
 Temp 1.43C Dewpoint -0.86C
 From 14:56:00 to now

Current values
 ++++ STATIC PRESSURE 905.12 mb
 ++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP 1.43 deg C
 ++++ DEW POINT -0.87 deg C

Flight B421 15:16:16
Heading 18 deg Speed 203 knots Height 3.5kft Press 888mb
Lat 52°24.0'N Long 4°30.0'W Wind 17 ms-1/ 276 deg
Temp 1.37C Dewpoint -2.46C
From 14:00:00 to now

Current values
++++ STATIC PRESSURE 888.6 mb
++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP 1.37 deg C
++++ DEW POINT -2.46 deg C

P4 end at 1000ft

R4 start

Run 4 end 1000ft

P5 down to 100ft from 1000ft

End R5 at 100ft - gentle climb out

P6 start

CPI seeing some ice up to 100um

CPI - gently snowing + mince pies

Just out of CT

End P6 FL220

Start R6 FL195

R6 end FL195

P7 start down to FL155

P7 end, R7 start at FL155

End R7 start P8 at FL155

End P8 at FL135

R8 start initially out of cloud

End R8 start P9 at FL135

P9 end start R9 at FL115

R9 end P10 start at FL115

P10 end start R10 at FL100

End R10 start P11 FL100 to FL90

P11 end start R11 at FL90

Just after end R11 at FL90

Start R12 at FL100

Flight Summary B421

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
Video	13:43:48	135	0.28kft	52.1N	0.6W						recording
shutters	13:44:06	135	0.28kft	52.1N	0.6W						closed
Start-Up	13:47:37	135	0.28kft	52.1N	0.6W						
ASP	13:53:25	073	0.28kft	52.1N	0.6W						open
T/O	14:00:26	212	0.28kft	52.1N	0.6W						Cranfield
Profile 1	14:01:26	317	1.4kft	52.1N	0.7W	14:07:30	245	10.0kft	52.4N	0.6W	from t/o surface to fl100
nev	14:05:47	352	8.2kft	52.3N	0.5W						zero
JW	14:06:26	339	9.2kft	52.4N	0.5W						zero
transit	14:08:19	242	10.0kft	52.3N	0.7W						
!	14:14:30	251	10.0kft	52.1N	1.3W						transit is run 1
Profile 2	14:15:40	250	10.1kft	52.1N	1.4W	14:23:17	266	18.0kft	51.9N	2.2W	also end r1
Run 2	14:23:17	266	18.0kft	51.9N	2.2W	14:33:20	246	18.0kft	51.7N	3.3W	
!	14:23:39	266	18.0kft	51.9N	2.3W						r2 fl180
!	14:23:59	266	18.0kft	51.9N	2.3W						psap flow off (cloud)
BBR	14:24:21	266	18.0kft	51.9N	2.4W						retract
Profile 3	14:33:20	246	18.0kft	51.7N	3.3W	14:37:51	261	22.0kft	51.5N	3.8W	
BBR	14:33:46	245	18.3kft	51.7N	3.4W						extend
Run 3	14:37:52	261	22.0kft	51.5N	3.8W	14:56:12	023	22.0kft	51.4N	5.8W	
BBR	14:39:47	269	22.0kft	51.5N	4.1W						retract
nev	14:40:15	267	22.0kft	51.5N	4.1W						zero
JW	14:40:57	266	22.0kft	51.5N	4.2W						zero
Profile 4	14:56:12	023	22.0kft	51.4N	5.8W	15:18:49	016	1.0kft	52.6N	4.5W	
p4	15:10:43	358	6.8kft	52.1N	4.8W						interrupt
p4	15:12:33	018	6.8kft	52.3N	4.7W						resumed

Profile 5	15:30:41	179	1.1kft	52.6N	5.4W	15:32:51	173	0.06kft	52.5N	5.3W	
Run 5	15:32:51	175	0.06kft	52.5N	5.3W	15:37:59	173	0.04kft	52.2N	5.2W	
r5	15:33:11	175	0.05kft	52.5N	5.3W						100ft
!	15:38:10	173	0.16kft	52.2N	5.2W						manouvre
Profile 6	15:39:51	035	0.67kft	52.2N	5.1W	15:57:35	218	22.0kft	52.3N	4.4W	
heimann	15:40:41	046	1.4kft	52.2N	5.0W						cal07
heimann	15:41:28	049	2.4kft	52.2N	5.0W						cal command ignored
heimann	15:44:02	000	5.4kft	52.4N	4.9W						cal 08 ok
cloud top	15:53:06	181	16.8kft	52.6N	4.4W						
!	15:58:06	269	22.0kft	52.2N	4.4W						manouvre
Run 6	16:00:07	314	19.5kft	52.3N	4.6W	16:10:09	351	19.5kft	52.8N	5.3W	
!	16:00:18	315	19.5kft	52.3N	4.6W						f1195
!	16:11:17	109	19.5kft	52.8N	5.2W						manouvre
Profile 7	16:11:35	128	19.5kft	52.8N	5.1W	16:15:10	192	15.5kft	52.5N	5.0W	
Run 7	16:15:10	192	15.5kft	52.5N	5.0W	16:25:19	347	15.5kft	52.8N	5.2W	
Profile 8	16:25:20	347	15.5kft	52.8N	5.2W	16:26:58	347	13.5kft	52.9N	5.2W	
!	16:27:09	359	13.5kft	52.9N	5.2W						manouvre
Run 8	16:28:54	167	13.5kft	52.9N	5.1W	16:39:26	334	13.5kft	52.2N	5.0W	
BBR	16:36:48	227	13.5kft	52.3N	4.8W						signal check ok
Profile 9	16:39:26	334	13.5kft	52.2N	5.0W	16:42:02	347	11.5kft	52.4N	5.1W	
Run 9	16:42:02	347	11.5kft	52.4N	5.1W	16:52:02	348	11.5kft	53.0N	5.1W	
Profile 10	16:52:02	348	11.5kft	53.0N	5.1W	16:54:10	133	10.0kft	53.0N	5.2W	
Run 10	16:54:11	133	10.0kft	53.0N	5.2W	17:04:11	115	10.0kft	52.6N	4.0W	
Profile 11	17:04:12	115	10.0kft	52.6N	4.0W	17:05:27	115	9.0kft	52.6N	3.8W	
Run 11	17:05:27	115	9.0kft	52.6N	3.8W	17:17:51	113	9.0kft	52.2N	2.4W	
!	17:18:28	113	9.3kft	52.1N	2.4W						pop up to f1100
Run 12	17:19:24	114	10.0kft	52.1N	2.2W						f1100

Plot - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Flight B421 17:26:22
 Heading 66 deg Speed 232 knots Height 10.0kft Press 696mb
 Lat 52°0.0'N Long 1°24.0'W Wind 25 ms-1/ 318 deg
 Temp -3.15C Dewpoint -4.43C

LWC Plot From: 14:56:00 To: now -

Save plot parameters as LWC

X 515.TIME FROM MIDNIGHT (secs)

655.THETA W	(K)
656.J01D	(E-5/S)
657.TECO NO	(ppb)
658.TECO NO2	(ppb)
659.TECO NOx	(ppb)
660.NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	(g m-3)
661.NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER	(g m-3)
662.GM1 ALTITUDE	(m)

Y1 535.J/W LIQUID WATER CONTENT (g m-3) Black Line Del

Y2 660.NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER (g m-3) Red Line Del

End R12 at FL100 start P12

Passed over Cranfield from W, turned NE and then N for RHT to align along R/W direction for missed approach at 50ft

Missed approach at 50ft

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B421

Date:17/12/08

Operator:PDR

Page 1 of 3

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks	
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size		Habit
Running Uman FSSP PADS manual settings used: Air speed 100 m/s Temperature 0 C Pressure 840 mb Hotwire Source 2 Vm 2DP- mounted horizontally rather than vertically due to a possible wing wiring problem. PCASP – Run for testing only. Data quality unknown. 2DP, 2DC tested and seem fine CDP switched on, connected fine, some data acquired Pcas flow 0.80 at 13:49 2dc voltages 2.4, 1.8 2dp voltage 4.2 ffssp voltage 3.6												
14:17:00	0		1			0			0			FI120
14:23:20	0		1			0			0			FI180
												End profile 2 start run 2
14:27:00	10		2			45			35000			
14:30:00	0		7			10			35000			
14:32:00												Rearmed 2dp to 1 fps due to noise
												End run 2 start profile 3
14:34:50	1		13			0			noise			FI190
14:37:50	0		13			0			noise			FI220
												End profile 3 start run 3
14:41:00	0		13			0			noise			
												2dp counts decreasing with time
												Noise improving to ~20 counts/cc
												From >1000
14:50	20		13			80			?			2dp registering zero counts but
												time since 1st refresh remains zero
14:56:10	0		13			0			0			End run 3 start profile 4

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B421

Date:17/12/08

Operator:PDR

Page 2 of 3

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:59:10	0		13		0			0			FI 190
15:02:40	10		13		0			0			FI 150
											Noise on 2dp restarted at 15:04:50 ~fl 120-130
15:10:30	10		14		3			8000			Interrupted descent
15:11:30								6000			Noise on 2dp decreasing while
15:12:00								3000			At const altitude
15:12:30								2000			Descent continued
15:14:45	30		14		0			1000			FI 50
15:16:00	30		14		0			30			FI 40
15:17:00	30		14		0			500			FI 30
15:17:45	20		14		0			1000			FI 20
15:18:50	20		14		0			0			FI 10 end profile 4 start run 4
15:22:00	20		14		0			0			Rearmed 2dp to 8 fps
15:29:00	40		15		0			0			Some precip seen in last 5 mins End run 4 start profile 5
											End profile 5 start run 5 @ 100ft
15:32:50	40		15		0			0			
15:36:00	40		16		0			0			
15:38:00	40		16		0			0			End run 5 start profile 6
15:41:00	30		16		0			0			FI 20
15:43:00	20		16		0			100			FI 40
15:46:15	10		17		10			400			FI 70
15:49:20	1		25		5			300			FI110
15: :00	0		25		10		snow	200		snow	FI 140
15:55:00	0		40		0			0			FI 190
15:57:35	1		40		0			0			FI 220 end profile 6
16:00:00	3		40		0			20000 Noise			Start run 6 @fl195
16:02:00	1		40		1			10000 Noise			
16:06:00	30		43		13		Aggreg	20000 Noise			
16:09:00	5		47		5		Aggreg	13000 Noise			
16:11:30	1		55		0			10000 Noise			End run 6 start profile 7
16:14:00	30		56		20		Ag	15000 Noise			FI 170
16:15:20	5		57		20		Ag	60000 Noise			End profile 7 start run 7 @fl 155

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B421

Date:17/12/08

Operator:PDR

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
16:20:00	10		68		20		Snow/ag	Noise			Rearmed 2dp to 1 fps Photographed pcasp – no icing evident
16:25:10	20				2		Snow/ag	Noise			End run 7 start profile 8
16:27:09	10				10		snow	noise			End profile 8 start run 8 @ fl135
16:30:00	3		122								Saw data on FSSP channel of SEADAS, but nothing is connected to it !!!
16:37:00	5		133		12		ag	Noise			
16:39:30	8		134		22		ag	10000 noise			End run 8 start profile 9
16:42:00	10		138		30		Ag/sm ic	10000 noise			End profile 9 start run 9 fl 115
16:50:30	40				5			200			Rearmed 2dp to 8fps
16:54:00	1				0			40		dend	Start run 10
16:56:00	1		370		100			5000			
17:03:45	20		459		5		Wet snow	400			End run 10 start profile 11
17:05:20	10		459		3		graupel	150			End profile 11 start run 11 fl 90
17:18:00	10		459		0			0			Endd run 11 start profile 12
17:19:30	20		459		0			0			End profile 12 start run 12
17:35:00	10		459		0			0			Fl 35
17:35:44	14										Fl 30
17:36:05	30										Fl 25
17:40:50	40										Fl 20
17:41:34	52										Fl 15
17:42:25	115										Fl 10
17:43:20	200										Fl 05
17:43:50	290										50 ft

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B421
Date of flight: 17/12/08

T/O:
Land:

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B421
Date of Flight: 17/12/08

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip		Size of Bnnn.dat = 261291
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read =49577 Blocks written = 49577 Bad reads =0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		Start = 0 End = 240000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 0 End =240000 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start =0 End = 240000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 173046.2 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 31</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X =1 Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size =1 Vol flow rate = 0.80
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check.

Flight:

B421

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B421

Date: 17/12/08

Issues

Instruments

Dropsondes	Nil
CVI -	ok – tip iced over, better when run with sp2 pump
Filters	not op
Neph	ok
PSAP	ok
Nev	check liquid water – may have depressed zero
WetNeph	not op
AMS	ok
Core Chem	CO data not recording on HORACE, looks like a hard zero
Heimann	operating – not calibrating
Cloud physics -	
PCASP	ok
2DP	noise/temperature change dependency
FFSSP	some spurious data on seadas
CPC	no network connection
2DS -	ok
CAPS -	ok
SMPS -	ok
Buck -	experimental operation ->ok

Aircraft

SatcomC	ops normal after reboot
MPDS	not op
ISDN Emails	Nil
Satcom-H Calls	Nil